

Teachers in Conversation with Jose Marti

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We present a book project, entitled “Teachers in Conversation with Jose Marti.” This book project invites scholars to think creatively about pedagogies for emancipation. This book is centered around the words and work of José Martí as common ground for a contemporary conversation about education and knowledge production in relation to economic/ecological/racial justice.

This book intends to bring Martí’s praxis into contemporary pedagogical work for critical education. Critical education in the tradition of critical pedagogy is believed to liberate people as a practice of freedom. Martí’s work in philosophy, culture and language and in changing the historical trajectory of Cuba has strengthened the development of a critical pedagogy that intersects power, consciousness, and organizing for transformation, social change and historical justice. This anachronic reflexive stance – with both historical and contemporary juxtapositions – is a critical foundation in knowledge production, cultural diversity and sustainability, and social change. Thus, the chapters will specifically bring to light the contemporary applications of Martí’s praxis and philosophy in the areas of curriculum and instruction, higher education and teacher education.

The first author of the book will present her interpretations and readings of the signs and symbols of Jose Marti from a Freirean and a semiotics lens. The second author will present applications of Mart’s philosophy in the development of the graduate studies in the sciences of education.

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